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Rethinking Blended Learning and Flipped Classroom Instructional Strategies for Global Best Practices in Science Education in Nigeria

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Abstract

The study is conducted out of the unending debates and clarion call for the ongoing blame on who or what is responsible for the falling standard of education and actualization of global best practices in Nigeria. This paper identifies and discusses blended learning and flipped classroom instructional strategies and how they can become the key to global best practices in science education in Nigeria. Thus, the main aim of this study is to examine how rethinking of blended learning and flipped classroom instructional strategies would enhance the actualization of global best practices in science education. It adopts exploratory research design, an approach that is based on qualitative analysis of the concepts of blended learning and flipped classroom learning instructional strategies for the actualization of global best practices in science education. Data were obtained specifically from reviewing of the literature. These secondary sources of data and the exploratory approach helped in arriving at findings. The method of analysis was explanatory in nature through adequate exegesis of the gathered information. Findings revealed that rethinking blended learning and flipped classroom instructional strategies would significantly enhance actualization of global best practices in science education, and was concluded to be a catalyst for enhancing global best practices in science education in Nigeria. It was recommended, among others, that Government and school administrators should digitalize and prioritize modern technology as part of the overall educational system and focusing on instructional improvement.

Keywords: Rethinking, Blended Learning and Flipped Classroom Instructional Strategies, Science Education Global Best Practices

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Introduction

Science education remains the bedrock of scientific and technological development. It provides opportunities for students to acquire relevant functional knowledge and skills that are associated with scientific processes needed for advancement in science and technology. In science education, students are encouraged to acquire and practice the scientific skills as they concern with finding answers to problems in a bid to understand and interpret natural phenomena. It is a field of study that exposes learners to the contents as well as the methodologies (processes) of acquiring scientific knowledge for practical application. Babajide (2015) opined that science education is an integrated field of study that considers both the subject matter of science discipline (biology, physics, chemistry, mathematics and integrated science) as well as the processes involved in the learning and teaching of science. There is no doubt that the level of development in a country is a true reflection of the standard of education. This implies that the higher the rate of development in a country, the higher the standard of education and vice versa. Dajal and Mohammed (2019) highlighted the problems of science education in Nigeria to include poor management and funding on the part of government, shortage of qualified teachers, poor attitudes of students towards the subject, poor teaching methods, lack of adequate laboratory equipment and insufficient exposure of students to laboratory activities, poor working condition and incentives on the part of science teachers resulting to poor attitudes to work, poor learning environment as well as poor socioeconomic background of students leading to lack of appropriate learning facilities. Given the deplorable state of science education and the relatively poor attention given to education by African leaders and university administrators, there is need to rethink classroom instructional strategies for the actualization of global best practices in order to enhance higher academic performance in science education.

Rethinking is the process of reconsidering, reviewing a decision or conclusion that has previously been made to determine whether the initial decision should be changed. Rethinking can occur immediately after a decision has been reached or at any time thereafter. Adam (2022) stated that rethinking is the ability to question, investigate and analyze your opinions and beliefs. And this is rethinking on the integration of

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blended learning and flipped classroom into teaching and learning processes and ensuring learners' needs are met in this context (Mishra, 2019). However, today's educators are aware that science is more than merely a discipline and that there are critical questions they need to address about the role and impact of science in education. Bizzo *et al.* (2002) examined rethinking science and technology education to meet the demands of future generations in a changing world of Brazil. The findings showed that liberal education; information assessment and argumentation in Science; educate rather than debate; towards learner-centered approach in senior secondary school science lessons; the role of teacher preparation for informal settings; understanding the educators and teacher perspectives as well as using suitable instructional materials to improve students' academic performance were the keys to meeting the demands of future generations in a changing world of Brazilians. Puamau (2005) investigated rethinking educational reform as a pacific perspective - National Institute of Education, Nanyang Technological University, Singapore. The study revealed that redesigning pedagogy; research, policy and practice are the keys to rethinking educational reform.

Global best practices refer to certain methods, techniques, mechanisms and practices that have been tested and found to be high results oriented at a global level. They are those practices that have worked for nations and produced results globally and as such, can serve as examples and templates; and set the pace for others to follow. It is a comprehensive tool designed to equip educators with a thoughtful process for in-depth professional and institutional self-reflection. They include such practices as continuous reevaluation of education standards, massive inclusion of vocational and technical trainings in higher education curricula; increase budgetary allocations to education and policy implementation beyond mere formulation, reengineering and implementing innovative teaching and instructional strategies for higher academic performance (Idowu, 2020). Udu (2018) stated that innovative practices in science education include the following practices: innovative practices in science education curriculum, innovative practices in science teaching and learning as well as innovative improvisation in science education. For effective teaching and learning to take place in the science classroom, the teacher is expected to communicate effectively and utilize appropriate innovative teaching strategies for achievement of stated objectives.

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Innovative teaching strategies involve the use of efficient teaching strategies to create better products, processes, technologies and ideas that are accepted by those in charge of education – teachers, administrators and parents. It combines external resources to design exciting and interactive curriculums for stimulating students' imagination, cultivating the ability of problem-solving, facilitating independent thinking as well as assist teachers in effective teaching (Lee & Kang, 2016). Effective teaching in schools requires functional teaching aids, flexibility, energy and commitment. It requires that the teachers should be able to provide learner's needs and understand the variations in learner's styles and approaches. Teachers can accomplish these requirements while making an optimal teaching-learning atmosphere by utilizing variety of teaching strategies and teaching styles. If teachers use a variety of teaching strategies, learners are exposed to both familiar and unfamiliar ways of learning that provide both comfort and tension during the process, ultimately giving learners multiple ways to excel (Kamboj & Singh, 2015). Kaltura (2023) opined that there are ten innovative teaching and learning strategies, namely flipped classroom, personalized learning, project-based learning, inquiry-bases learning, jigsaws, ask open-ended questions, peer teaching, blended learning, feedback as well as active learning. However, the focus of this study is to rethink blended learning and flipped classroom innovative teaching and learning strategies as means to actualize global best practices in science education.

In the late 1990s, blended learning strategies emerged as a new teaching method for distance, learning through the application of technology and the internet to improve students' learning and encourage teachers to change their conventional methods of teaching and shift learning to a more student-centered model rather than a teacher-centered learning model (Smith & Hill, 2019). Blended learning combines both virtual and physical environments. It is a form of learning that combines the best of direct classroom learning and learning through the internet by using its applications (Volchenkova, 2016). It has become an emerging trend in the field of education all over the world. This is due to the global impact of digital technologies on education (Fernandez *et al.*, 2021). It has also become even more relevant in education as one of the pedagogical methods to address the challenges faced by educators and learners in the

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education field (Tempornsin *et al.*, 2019). Blended learning is a combination of online and face-to-face activities for classroom instruction or other training modalities to help develop new knowledge and skills that can be transferred to the workplace environment. The use of blended learning is expanding globally (Boeren, 2019). Using the blended learning approach to learning allows instructional facilitators with the opportunity to personalize learning for every participant in any typical leadership training program (Gurley, 2018). However, any student who may not learn well, the use of blended learning strategy may be the great advantage as it combines both online and face-to-face training that could build a more efficient way to offer participants a balanced approach to learning.

Flipped classroom learning is a pedagogical method in which teachers shift direct learning out of the large group learning space or classroom and move it into the individual learning space with the help of one of several technologies (Wulandari, 2021). Flipped classroom learning refers to a teaching-learning strategy in which students gain first exposure to new material outside of class, usually via lectures, videos or reading of other assigned materials, and then the class time is used to do the harder work of assimilating that knowledge through problem-solving, discussions and debates (Chiquito *et al.*, 2019). In flipped classroom learning strategy, teachers record or create videos of themselves or other experts teaching, or download video lessons from internet sites. The videos are available on VCDs, DVDs, internet and other storage devices, for students to access whenever and wherever it is convenient. Leo *et al.* (2021) added that the flipped learning classroom requires flexible environments, a shift in learning culture, intentional content, dedicated and professional educators.

Literature Review

Aslam (2018) carried out a comparative study on the use of blended learning in middle school science with traditional teaching. Results of the study showed that students who were taught with the blended learning model had better scores than those who attended traditional instruction. Almasaeid (2018) examined the effect of using blended learning strategy on achievement and attitudes teaching science among 9th grade students. Findings of the study revealed that using blended learning strategy to teach science has a

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positive impact in achievement skills and attitudes. There was high level of performance on achievement test as a whole after applying blended learning strategy. Alsalhi *et al.* (2019) also investigated the effects of blended learning on ninth grade students' achievement in science and their attitudes towards using it. Findings of the study revealed that there were statistically significant differences between the experimental and the control groups, with the results in favour of the experimental group, and the experimental group's attitudes were also more positive towards the use of blended learning.

Shao and Liu (2021) explored the effect of flipped classrooms on students' learning performance compared to traditional classrooms via meta-analysis. The results indicated that the flipped classroom can improve students' academic performance. Chen *et al.* (2018) compared the efficacy of the flipped classroom with traditional lecture-based learning, and found that the students who experienced flipped classrooms had higher learning performance than those who learned in traditional classrooms. Ugwuanyia *et al.* (2020) determine the effect of flipped classroom strategy on achievement and retention among senior secondary school physics students, and found that flipped classroom is more superior in enhancing the achievement of physics students.

Theoretical Framework

Socio-Cultural Theory was propounded by Lev Vygotsky in 1934. The theory posits that social interaction plays a critical role in students' learning. Through such social interactions, students go through continuous process of learning. Socio-cultural theory states that individuals are active participants in the creation of their own knowledge. Vygotsky's socio-cultural theory asserts that learning is an essentially social process in which the support of parents, caregivers, peers, the wider society and culture plays a crucial role in the development of higher psychological functions. Social constructivism supports that successful teaching and learning is heavily dependent on interpersonal interaction and the use of gadget like phones, projectors, smart-boards, tablets and laptops. In view of this, Vygotsky viewed teaching and learning as what cannot be judged by what the child can do when working alone but rather how far ahead

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the learner can go when offered some assistance by a mere experienced person (teacher). Vygotsky stated that there are two parts of a learner's developmental level: the actual developmental level and the potential developmental level. The Zone of Proximal Development is the distance between the actual developmental level as determined by independent problem solving and the level of potential development as determined through problem solving under adult guidance, or in collaboration with more capable peers. The Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) can also be described as the area between what a learner can do by himself and that which can be attained with the help of a more knowledgeable other, be it an adult or peer. The more knowledgeable other (MKO), shares knowledge with the student to bridge the gap between what is known and what is not known. Once the student has expanded his knowledge, the actual developmental level has been expanded and the ZPD has shifted. The ZPD is always changing as the student expands and gains knowledge, so scaffolding and blended instructions must constantly be individualized to address the changing ZPD of each student. The relevance of this theory to this study is that it is the teachers' job to move students forward in their academic process. Through blended and flipped classroom strategies, the students' zones of the proximal development can be reached as their teachers provide assistances.

Statement of the problem

Given the deplorable state of tertiary education and the relatively poor attention given to education by Nigerian leaders, university administrators and educational stakeholders, many Nigerians students now seek for admissions abroad to actualize their academic pursuits. Those that were not performing well in their academic are now becoming first class products and have global relevant. This is a worrisome situation in the Nigeria educational standard. Over the years, there has been an ongoing blame on 'who or what' is responsible for the fall in the standard of education in Nigeria. This has posed serious threats to the future of our education, especially in the areas of science and technology. Today, Europe and the Asian Tigers have considered to have made significant progress in quality of higher education and are used as benchmarks for best practices in higher education. From empirical document analysis, the global best practices include such

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practices as continuous reevaluation of education standards, massive inclusion of vocational and technical trainings in higher education curricula; increase budgetary allocations to education and policy implementation beyond mere formulation, reengineering and implementing innovative teaching and instructional strategies for higher academic performance. Studies reviewed of extant relevant literature have showed the actualization of these global best practices has impacted positively on higher quality of education in Europe and among the Asian Tigers where Nigerians now highly sort for. Therefore, this study sought to rethink blended learning and flipped learning classroom teaching strategies and how these methods can become the key to global best practices in science education in Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study is to rethink science education for the actualization of global best practices in Nigeria. Specifically, this study seeks to:

1. Examine how rethinking of blended learning instructional strategies would enhance the actualization of global best practices in science education in Nigeria.
2. Examine how rethinking of flipped classroom learning instructional strategies would enhance the actualization of global best practices in science education in Nigeria.
3. Evaluate the effects of rethinking blended learning instructional strategies for the actualization of global best practices in science education in Nigeria.
4. Evaluate the effects of rethinking flipped classroom learning instructional strategies for actualization of global best practices in science education in Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions, therefore, emanate from the above objectives:

1. How would a rethink of blended learning instructional strategies enhance actualization of global best practices in science education in Nigeria?
2. How would a rethink of flipped classroom learning instructional strategies enhance actualization of global best practices in science education in Nigeria?
3. What would be the effects of rethinking blended learning instructional strategies

- for the actualization of global best practices in science education in Nigeria?
4. What would be the effects of rethinking flipped classroom learning instructional strategies for the actualization of global best practices in science education in Nigeria?

Methodology

This study adopted exploratory research design, an approach that is based on qualitative analysis of the concepts of blended learning and flipped classroom learning instructional strategies for the actualization of global best practices in science education. This research design was best adopted for the study due to the nature of the subject matter, the challenge of data collection and the specific questions to answer. Data were obtained specifically from the review of extant literature, including textbooks, periodicals and a range of relevant secondary sources. These secondary sources of data and the exploratory approach help in arriving at findings.

Discussions and Findings

How to Rethink Blended Learning Instructional Strategies to Enhance Actualization of Global Best Practices

1. Ensure that the goals and method of online and face-to-face components are aligning and coherent. This means that there must be clear vision of what the students are to achieve and how the different modes of instruction will support it.
2. Engagement and motivation of learners throughout the subject matter. Teachers need to design the course in the way that appeal to different learning style, provides feedback and support, create sense of community and collaboration. The teacher needs to monitor the learner's progress and participation and intervene when necessary to address any issues or concerns.
3. The teacher should use a reliable infrastructure that is accessible. That is, the teacher should choose appropriate tools and platforms that suit the learning objectives, content and learners. It should be tested and troubleshoot before and during the cause of learning and provide technical support and guidance to learners.

4. Redesign and implement effective assessment and evaluation strategies that measure the learner's outcome and satisfactions. That is, align the assessment and evaluation methods with the learning methods, use a variety of tools and techniques to collect and analyze data; provide timely and constructive feedbacks to learners and use the result to improve the blended learning course.

What would be the Effects of Rethinking Blended Learning Instructional strategies for the Actualization of global best Practices?

1. Blended learning offers teacher more flexibility, autonomy and creativity in designing and delivery of resource using online platforms and tools. By using online platforms and tools, the teacher can create engaging and personalized learning experiences for the learners as well as access the variety of resources and data to support the instruction.
2. Blended learning can provide learners with more opportunities, choices and control over their learning process. By combining online and face-to-face teaching modes, learners can assess the contents and activities at their pace and place as well as interact with their teachers and peers in different ways. It would also enhance learner's motivation, engagement and world-class achievement, as they can benefit from social and emotional support of the classroom.
3. Blended learning would make learning more efficient and fun if students come into the classroom, having watched lesson videos and engage in activities on slide desk. Teachers can spend the entire class period targeting specific learner's confusion and answering difficult questions.
4. Blended learning encourages interactive communication. By using online tools such as discussion forums and wikis, students can work together to complete projects and assignments. These help students develop critical collaborative skills and allow students to learn from each other. One of the ways of encouraging collaboration in blended learning is to create group projects that require students to work together. Teachers can also use online discussion forums to facilitate group discussions and encourage students to share their ideas and perspectives.

How to rethink flipped Classroom learning Instructional Strategy to enhance the Actualization of global best Practices

1. Communicate clearly and frequently with students, parents and administrators about effective and efficient implementation, the goals, benefits and expectations of flipped classroom.
2. The online materials should be selected carefully and creatively. The materials should be relevant, engaging and appropriate for the students' level and learning style.
3. In-class activities should also be designed collaboratively and flexibly with the online materials in mind.
4. Assessment of students' learning should be comprehensive and formative, with both online and in-class data used to measure progress and achievement.

What would be the Effects of rethinking flipped Classroom learning Instructional Strategy to the Actualization of global best Practices?

1. Flipped classroom enables students to learn concepts at their own pace and revisit content as often as they need to.
2. Flipped classroom helps students gain understanding of a concept prior to class, so they can feel confident during classroom discussions and activities.
3. Flipped classroom helps students learn skills for self-regulating their school and work activities.
4. It gives room for personalization and putting students into groups based on their level of understanding so as to encourage group participation and learning.

Conclusion

Rethinking of blended learning and flipped classroom learning instructional strategies to enhance the actualization of global best practices in science education in Nigeria was examined. The following were drawn from the findings of this study: that blended learning instructional strategies would create a more effective, dynamic and engaging learning experience that meets the needs of modern learners, that flipped classroom in particular would create a reversed experience where the student learns the concept on

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their own and then applies and reinforces what they learned during classroom time through the teacher's facilitation. This method encourages self-paced learning and students who are in charge of their educational journeys. Teachers become facilitators who guide students. This method of teaching and learning can help students better absorb information and gain a higher understanding of how to apply it as obtainable globally. Finally, it can be concluded that rethinking of blended learning and flipped classroom learning instructional strategies is a catalyst for the actualization of global best practices in science education in Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion drawn, the following recommendations were proffered:

1. All stakeholders in science education should embrace blended learning and flipped classroom learning instructional strategies.
2. Government and school administrators should digitalize and prioritize modern technology as part of the overall educational system and focus more on instructional improvement. These will reduce costs of training abroad, increase national impact on science education and offer information and skill development educationists.

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